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**>>ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES,
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
AND FOOD PRODUCTION<<**

OPORPH 2023

**November 9-10th, 2023
Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina**

**Environmental resources, sustainable development
and food production – OPORPH 2023: Book of Abstracts**

The Symposium is the traditional meeting that takes place every second year, and this Book is a serial publication that accompanies it. The Book contains the abstracts of plenary lectures and oral presentations, along with the posters' abstracts, presented at VIII International scientific-professional symposium "Environmental resources, sustainable development and food production" – OPORPH 2023, held on November 9-10 2023 in Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina, organized by Faculty of Technology, University of Tuzla in cooperation with Association of Chemist of Tuzla Canton.

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THE INFLUENCE OF SILICA GEL AS A BLEACHING AGENT ON THE QUALITY AND COMPOSITION OF SUNFLOWER OIL

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In this paper, samples of different types of silica gel with a granulation of 0-40 μm , produced by the company Zeochem (Zvornik, Bosnia and Herzegovina), were used for bleaching raw sunflower oil from the company Victoriaoil (Šid, Serbia). The bleaching of raw sunflower oil was carried out in laboratory conditions, at a temperature of 95 °C, a contact time of 30 minutes and doses of the bleaching agent (% m/m): 0.2; 1.0; 2.0; 3.0. For the characterization of silica gel, instrumental methods were used: XRD, FTIR, SEM/EDS, BET and laser method. The bleaching effects of sunflower oil were tested using standard methods for determining oil characteristics (peroxide number, color, acid number, iodine number) and its composition (soap, chlorophyll and phosphorus content, saturated and unsaturated fatty acids). The bleaching effects of crude sunflower oil with silica gel were compared with those of commercial bleaching earth.

The obtained results showed that the tested sunflower oil was of the linoleic type, and bleaching caused a slight change in its composition and characteristics (the obtained values were in accordance with the prescribed norms). It can be concluded that the effects of bleaching sunflower oil with silica gel samples are close to the effects of bleaching with commercial earth.

Keywords: raw sunflower oil; silica gel; bleaching earth; composition and characteristics of bleached sunflower oil